

Some New Reactions of Cinnamoylmorpholine Derivatives with Amino Acids

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Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acids [2-13] and some of the corresponding methyl esters [14-18] were prepared. Hydrazinolysis of the methyl esters in methanol yielded the corresponding hydrazides [19-23]. Coupling of the amino acid derivatives [2-13] with amino acid methyl ester hydrochlorides in THF-Et₃N medium using the dicyclohexylcarbodiimide method afforded the desired dipeptide methyl esters [25-30]. Some of the compounds [2-30] were found to be active against a number of microorganisms.

Several nitrogen, oxygen, and sulphur containing heterocyclic compounds incorporating amino acid residues were found to possess interesting biological properties¹. Recently, we have reported the synthesis and structure activity relationship of a variety of aromatic and heterocyclic derivatives of amino acids and dipeptides². Moreover, various aromatic sulphonylamino acid derivatives possess various biological activities³.

The reaction of cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl chloride (1)* with the appropriate amino acid in water-THF-triethylamine medium yielded the desired cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acids (2-13). Synthesis of cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acid methyl esters (14-18) was carried out by treating cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl amino acids (2-13) with methanol and thionyl chloride at -10°. The time required for completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc. Complete acid hydrolysis of compound 9 or 17 (6N HCl, 24 h, 105°) followed by subsequent paper chromatography yielded a positive spot of leucine. Hydrazinolysis of the methyl esters (14-18) in methanol afforded the corresponding hydrazides (19-23) which gave the benzidine and silver nitrate reactions.

For the preparation of cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyldipeptide methyl esters (24-30), the appropriate amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride was reacted with cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acids in THF-Et₃N medium using dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) method. The compounds were purified by repeated recrystallisations from the appropriate solvent and the products were

chromatographically homogeneous. Complete acid hydrolysis of compound 26 (6N HCl, 105°, for 24 h) and subsequent chromatography gave positive spots of both alanine and leucine. The dipeptide methyl esters gave blue coloured 1:1 copper(II) complexes exhibiting λ_{max} at 640-660 nm characteristic of normal dipeptide esters⁴.

The structures of all the compounds (Table I)

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	M.p.** °C	R _f	[α] ₂₀ ^D †
2	Gly	253-55	0.94	—
3	L-Ala	230-32	0.56	+13.1
4	DL-Ala	242-44	0.79	—
5	B-Ala	235-37	0.78	—
6	L-Val	215-17	0.70	+16.6
7	DL-Val	248-50	0.60	—
8	L-Ser	198-200	0.68	+17.1
9	L-Leu	232-34	0.73	+14.3
10	DL-Leu	235-37	0.75	—
11	L-Phe	244-46	0.71	+22.1
12	L-Tyr	208-10	0.57	+24.6
13	L-Pro	214-16	0.62	+25.6
14	Gly-OMe	143-45	0.64	—
15	DL-Ala-OMe	132-34	0.82	—
16	L-Val-OMe	115-17	0.86	+19.6
17	L-Leu-OMe	98-100	0.65	+8.0
18	DL-Leu-OMe	105-07	0.69	—
19	Gly-N ₂ H ₃	175-77	0.71	—
20	DL-Ala-N ₂ H ₃	185-87	0.48	—
21	L-Val-N ₂ H ₃	70-72	0.44	—
22	L-Leu-N ₂ H ₃	175-77	0.69	+8.5
23	DL-Leu-N ₂ H ₃	192-94	0.53	—
24	Gly-L-Leu-OMe	166-68	0.81	+14.1
25	DL-Ala-DL-Ala-OMe	160-62	0.90	—
26	L-Ala-L-Leu-OMe	148-50	0.69	+12.5
27	L-Val-DL-Ala-OMe	155-57	0.61	11.6
28	DL-Val-DL-Ala-OMe	140-42	0.37	—
29	L-Leu-L-Leu-OMe	160-62	0.54	+9.5
30	DL-Leu-L-Leu-OMe	179-81	0.60	+7.5

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

** Crystallisation solvent: Methanol-water for 2-18, 24-30; ethanol-water for 19-23. † Optical rotation [α]₂₀^D (c=5, in DMF at λ_{max} 589 at 20°).

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were assigned on the basis of elemental analysis, chromatographic studies, spot-tests, ir and nmr spectral data.

Biological screening : The antimicrobial activity of the compounds (2–30) were tested using the hole plate and filter paper disc methods⁶ against gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria. A qualitative screening was performed on all compounds, while quantitative assay was carried out on active compounds only. The results were compared with the activity of compound 1 (Table 2). Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl chloride (1) was antimicrobially inactive.

Cinnamoylmorpholine 4-sulphonylamino acids (2–13). *General procedure:* Triethylamine (5 ml) followed by cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl chloride (1; 0.11 mol) were added portionwise with stirring during 30 min to a solution of the appropriate amino acid (0.1 mol) in water (25 ml)–THF (15 ml) mixture keeping the temperature 10°, the solution was then concentrated under reduced pressure and water (30 ml) added. The mixture was then cooled to 0° and acidified with 2*N* HCl until acidic (pH 5). The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from methanol-water (yield 44–66%). All compounds were found

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY (A) AND MINIMAL INHIBITORY CONCENTRATION (MIC) IN $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ OF THE BIOLOGICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	<i>B. cereus</i>		<i>C. utilis</i>		<i>S. lutea</i>		<i>B. sphaericus</i>		<i>P. seruginosa</i>	
	A	MIC	A	MIC	A	MIC	A	MIC	A	MIC
24	+++	220	++	340	++	440	++	415	+	475
25	++	325	++	410	—	—	—	—	—	—
26	+++	210	+++	210	—	—	+	495	—	—
27	+++	230	+++	345	+	500	+	500	+	470
28	—	—	++	410	+	500	—	—	—	—
29	++	360	++	400	+++	200	+	465	+++	270
30	+++	240	+++	360	+++	270	++	350	+++	210

* Activity : (+++)=high, (++)=moderate, (+)=slight, (—)=inactive.

Among the compounds, cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acids, methyl esters and the corresponding hydrazides were found to be inactive against the tested microorganisms while dipeptide derivatives (24–30) were found to be active towards the tested microorganisms. Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyldipeptide methyl esters containing L-leucine residue, such as compounds 26, 29 and 30 were found to possess higher antimicrobial activity than the corresponding dipeptides containing DL-alanine residues (25, 27, 28). Most of the dipeptide methyl esters were found to possess various antimicrobial activities toward all the tested microorganisms (Table 2). Moreover, the biological action of the cinnamoylmorpholine derivatives depends on the amino acid constitution, its configuration and the C-terminal protecting groups in these compounds.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Thin layer chromatography (R_f) was carried out on silica gel-GI using n-butanol-acetic acid-water (4 : 1 : 1) as the solvent system and iodine as detection reagent. Optical rotation was measured in a Bellingham-Stanely polarimeter ($c=5$ in dimethylformamide) at λ_{max} 589 nm using 5 cm tube at 20°. Ir spectra were taken on a Shimadzu 440 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra (DMSO- d_6) on a Varian EM-360L instrument using TMS as internal standard.

Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl chloride (1): It was prepared⁴ by the treatment of cinnamoylmorpholine with chlorosulphonic acid using the procedure described earlier, yield, 60%.

chromatographically homogeneous (detection with iodine or benzidine) and showed negative ninhydrin reaction; ν_{max} 3 300, 3 080 (NH, SO₂NH), 1 420 (CH=CH), 1 725 (C=O), 1 360 cm^{-1} (SO₂NH) and other bands characteristic of the cinnamoylmorpholine and amino acid residues; 12.2 (1H, COOH), 8.7–8.2 (aromatic and morpholine protons), 4.5 (CH=CH), 7.4 (1H, NH) and other protons assignable to the amino acid residues.

Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acid methyl esters (14–18). *General procedure:* A solution of cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acid (0.01 mol) in absolute methanol (80 ml) was cooled to –10° and pure thionyl chloride (0.011 mol) was then added dropwise during 30 min keeping the temperature of the mixture below 0°. It was then stirred for additional 3–4 h at room temperature, kept overnight and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. Methanol was added to it and re-evaporated several times and the residual solid material was recrystallised from methanol-water (yield 53–65%). The compounds were chromatographically homogeneous when developed with iodine or benzidine and hydroxamate reactions and gave a negative ninhydrin test; ν_{max} 1 760, 1 725 (CO), 1 750 cm^{-1} (COOCH₃) and other bands characteristic of the amino acid and cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl residues; δ 4.0 (3H, COOCH₃), 8.2 (1H, NH) and other signals in support of the assigned structures.

Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acid hydrazides (19–23). *General procedure:* A solution of cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonylamino acid methyl esters (0.001 mol) in absolute methanol (25 ml) and

hydrazine hydrate (85% ; 0.003 mol) in methanol (25 ml) was kept for 24 h at 0°. The crystalline product was washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol-water (yield 44–74%). The compounds were chromatographically homogeneous when detected with iodine or benzidine and gave negative hydroxamate reaction ; ν_{\max} 3 430, 3 300 (NH, NH₂), 1 550 (CONHNH₂), 3 300, 1 160 cm⁻¹ (SO₂NH) and other bands assignable the cinnamoylmorpholine and amino acid moieties.

Cinnamoylmorpholine 4-sulphonyldipeptide methyl (24–30). General procedure : Triethylamine (2 ml) was added to a solution of amino acid methyl ester hydrochloride (0.0011 mol) in THF (50 ml). The mixture was stirred at 20° for 3 min and cooled to 0°. Cinnamoylmorpholine-4-sulphonyl amino acid (0.001 mol) in THF (20 ml) and dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) (1.59 g) were then added to it. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h at 0° and for another 2 h at room temperature. Dicyclohexylurea was filtered off, acetic acid (1 ml) was added, the solution filtered, the filtrate evaporated under reduced pressure and the residual solid was recrystallised from methanol-water (yield 53–77%). The compounds were soluble in alcohols, DMF and dioxane but insoluble in water and ether. The dipeptide were chromatographically homogeneous when detected with iodine or benzidine and gave negative ninhydrin reaction ; ν_{\max} 3 300, 3 100 (NH, CONH, SO₂NH), 1 750 (C=O), 1 320 cm⁻¹ (COO-CH₃) and other characteristic bands due to cinnamoylmorpholine and dipeptide moieties ; δ 3.3 (3H, COOCH₃), 8.0 (1H, NH), 8.2–8.7 (aromatic and cinnamoylmorpholine residue) and other bands supporting the structures.

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